

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1910	Jacques Duchesne-Guillemin	1931	1931	1986		French linguist, philologist, and orientalist	1910-2012
1910	Mary Haas	1932	1935	1977	w	American linguist (North American Indian languages, Thai, and historical linguistics)	1910-1996
1910	Raphael Patai	1932	1936	1976		Hungarian-Jewish ethnographer, historian, Orientalist and anthropologist	1910-1996
1910	Harry Hawthorn	1932	1932	1976		New Zealand-Canadian Anthropologist and museum curator	1910-2006
1910	Jozef Vergote	1932	1932	1978		Belgian Flemish Egyptologist and Coptologist	1910-1992
1910	Jacques Chailley	1933	1952	1974		French musicologist and composer	1910-1999
1910	Jaroslav Rudnyckyj	1934	1937	1976		Ukrainian-Canadian linguist and lexicographer (etymology and onomastics), folklorist, bibliographer, travel writer, and publicist	1910-1995
1910	Herbert Penzl	1934	1934	1979		Austrian-American philologist and historical linguist	1910-1995
1910	Heinz Politzer	1934	1950	1978		Austrian-American academic and author	1910-1978
1910	Dieter Cunz	1934	1934	1969		German-American professor of German language and literature	1910-1969
1910	Arthur Thomas Hatto	1934		1977		British English scholar of German studies	1910-2010
1910	Reinhold Olesch	1935	1935	1975		German linguist, Slavic studies Professor	1910-1990
1910	Käthe Bosse-Griffiths	1935	1935	1994	w	German-British (Wales) Egyptologist and writer in the Welsh language	1910-1998
1910	Phyllis Kaberry	1935	1938	1976	w	American social anthropologist (the study of women in various societies)	1910-1977
1910	Lilli Gjerløw	1936	1962	1980	w	Norwegian archivist	1910-1998
1910	William Bedell Stanford	1936		1980		Irish classical scholar and senator	1910-1984
1910	Gertrud Pätsch	1937	1937	1970	w	German ethnologist and philologist (Kartvelian studies)	1910-1994
1910	W. Nelson Francis	1937	1937	1990		American linguist	1910-2002
1910	Jean-Paul Vinay	1937		1976		French-Canadian linguist, one of the pioneers in translation studies	1910-1999
1910	Edmund Leach	1937	1947	1979		British social anthropologist	1910-1989
1910	Conrad M. Arensberg	1937	1937	1980		American anthropologist and scholar	1910-1997
1910	Ida Halpern	1938	1938	1980	w	Austrian-Canadian ethnomusicologist	1910-1987

1910	Fei Xiaotong	1938	1938	2005	Chinese pioneering researcher and professor of sociology and anthropology	1910-2005
1910	Villem Raam	1938		1982	Estonian art historian, art critic and conservator-restorer	1910-1996
1910	France Bezlaj	1939	1939	1991	Slovenian linguist	1910-1993
1910	Edwin O. Reischauer	1939	1939	1981	American educator and professor (japanologist)	1910-1990
1910	Pranė Dundulienė	1939	1954	1991 w	Lithuanian ethnographer	1910-1991
1910	Jack Plumley	1939	1939	1977	British Anglican priest, Egyptologist and academic	1910-1999
1910	Emeline Hill Richardson	1939	1939	1979 w	American notable classical archaeologist and Etruscan scholar	1910-1999
1910	Lin Yaohua	1940	1940	2000	Chinese leading Chinese sociologist and anthropologist	1910-2000
1910	Wilhelmina Feemster Jashemski	1942	1942	1984 w	American Classical scholar	1910-2007
1910	Georgi D. Sotirov	1943	1943	1986	Bulgarian scholar (Historian, Philologist)	1910-1986
1910	María Rosa Lida de Malkiel	1944	1947	1962 w	Argentinean philologist and Hispanist medievalist	1910-1962
1910	Charles Dédéyan	1944	1944	1984	French Romance philologist, literature comparatist and specialist of French literature of Armenian origin	1910-2003
1910	Jean Rousset	1944	1953	1976	Swiss literary critic on French literature, and in particular on Baroque literature of the late Renaissance and early seventeenth century	1910-2002
1910	Paul Saagpakk	1947	1947	1981	Estonian linguist who compiled a standard reference dictionary of the Estonian language	1910-1996
1910	Philippe Marçais	1948	1952	1980	French Arabist and politician	1910-1984
1910	Veronica Seton-Williams	1948	1957	1977 w	British-Australian Archaeologist who excavated in Egypt and the Near East.	1910-1992
1910	Willard R. Espy	1950	1959	1992	American editor, philologist, writer, poet, and local historian	1910-1999
1910	Tsien Tsuen-hsui	1950	1957	1978	Chinese sinologist and librarian, professor of Chinese literature and library science, curator of its East Asian Library	1910-2015
1910	Alexander Sahinian	1955		1982	Armenian architectural historian	1910-1982
1911	Eli Fischer-Jørgensen	1932	No	1981 w	Danish professor of linguistics	1911-2010
1911	J. L. Austin	1933		1960	British linguist (Philosophy of language, philosophy of mind, ethics, philosophy of perception)	1911-1960
1911	George Ivaşcu	1933	1933	1988	Romanian journalist, literary critic, and communist militant	1911-1988

1911	Raven I. McDavid Jr.	1933	1935	1977	American linguist (dialectology)	1911-1984
1911	Augusto Marinoni	1933	1933	1981	Italian professor of romance philology	1911-1997
1911	André Leroi-Gourhan	1933	1933	1982	French archaeologist, paleontologist, paleoanthropologist, and anthropologist with an interest in technology and aesthetics and a penchant for philosophical reflection	1911-1986
1911	Giovanni Semerano	1934	1934	1973	Italian philologist and linguist (languages of Ancient Mesopotamia)	1911-2005
1911	Naphtali Lewis	1934	1934	1983	American papyrologist who published extensively on subjects ranging from the ancient papyrus industry to government in Roman Egypt	1911-2005
1911	Irving Goldman	1934	1934	1980	American anthropologist	1911-2002
1911	Ernst Risch	1935	1935	1988	Swiss hellenist and philologist	1911-1988
1911	Max Gluckman	1936	1936	1975	South African and British social anthropologist.	1911-1975
1911	Antonio Tovar	1936	1941	1979	Spanish philologist, linguist and historian	1911-1985
1911	Kenneth Oakley	1936	1938	1969	British English physical anthropologist, palaeontologist and geologist	1911-1981
1911	Dina Lévi-Strauss	1936		1974 w	Italian-French ethnologist, anthropologist, sociologist, and philosopher, who conducted cultural research in South America	1911-1999
1911	David G. Mandelbaum	1936	1936	1978	American anthropologist	1911-1987
1911	Alfred Felix Landon Beeston	1937	1937	1979	British English Orientalist best known for his studies of Arabic language and literature, and of ancient Yemeni inscriptions, as well as the history of pre-Islamic	1911-1995
1911	Herbert Halpert	1937	1942	1979	American anthropologist and folklorist, specialised in the collection and study of both folk song and narrative	1911-2000
1911	Weston La Barre	1937	1937	1977	American anthropologist, best known for his work in ethnobotany, particularly with regard to Native-American religion, and for his application of psychiatric and psychoanalytic theories to ethnography	1911-1996
1911	Hans Walter Wolff	1937	1942	1978	German Protestant theologian	1911-1993
1911	Joan Turville-Petre	1937		1965 w	British noted academic at Oxford University, England, in the field of Anglo-Saxon, Icelandic and Scandinavian language studies	1911-2006

1911	Robert A. Hall Jr.	1938		1976	American linguist and specialist in the Romance languages	1911-1997
1911	Oliver Gurney	1939	1939	1978	British Assyriologist and a leading scholar of the Hittites	1911-2001
1911	Eric Gardner Turner	1939		1978	British English papyrologist and classicist	1911-1983
1911	Zabihollah Safa	1940	1943	1969	Iranian scholar and professor Emeritus of Iranian Studies	1911-1999
1911	St. Clair Drake	1940	1954	1976	American Afro sociologist and anthropologist whose scholarship and activism led him to document much of the social turmoil of the 1960s, establish some of the first Black Studies programs in American universities, and contribute to the independence movement in Ghana	1911-1990
1911	Philip Drucker	1940		1955	American anthropologist and archaeologist who specialized in the Native American peoples of the Northwest Coast of North America	1911-1982
1911	Francis Woodman Cleaves	1942	1942	1980	American Sinologist, linguist, and historian, the founder of Sino-Mongolian studies in America	1911-1995
1911	Donald Collier	1942		1970	American archaeologist, ethnologist, and museologist	1911-1995
1911	Sesto Prete	1945	1945	1978	Italian-American philologist and paleographer	1911-1991
1911	John DeFrancis	1946	1948	1976	American linguist, sinologist, author of Chinese language textbooks, lexicographer of Chinese dictionaries	1911-2009
1911	Hilda Kuper	1947	1947	1977 w	Zimbabwean Swazi social anthropologist most notable for her extensive work on Swazi culture	1911-1992
1911	W. D. Davies	1948	1948	1985	British Welsh Congregationalist minister, theologian, author and professor of religion	1911-2001
1911	Louis-Charles Damais	1949		1966	French researcher at the École française d'Extrême-Orient (EFEO)	1911-1966
1911	Ernesto Guerra Da Cal	1951	1951	1977	Spanish-American Galician writer and philologist	1911-1994
1911	Louis Dumont	1951	1955	1995	French anthropologist	1911-1998
1911	Vera D. Rubin	1952	1952	1985 w	American anthropologist and the director of the Research Institute for the Study of Man	1911-1985
1912	Walter J. Ong	1929	1955	1984	American Jesuit priest , professor of English literature, cultural and religious historian and philosopher	1912-2003

1912 Jacques Soustelle	1933	1937	1975	French anthropologist (Pre-Columbian civilizations), museum director, politician	1912-1990
1912 Gianfranco Contini	1933	1933	1982	Italian academic and philologist	1912-1990
1912 J. Mitchell Morse	1933	1952	1979	American writer and literary critic	1912-2004
1912 Jean Bousquet	1933	1933	1983	French the 20th-century Hellenist	1912-1996
1912 Olof Gigon	1934	1934	1982	Swiss classical philologist	1912-1998
1912 Pierre Grimal	1934	1944	1985	French historian, classicist and Latinist	1912-1996
1912 Kenneth L. Pike	1935	1942	1979	American linguist and anthropologist	1912-2000
1912 Horace Mitchell Miner	1935	1937	1980	American anthropologist (languages of his time that were still closely tied to the earth and agricultural practices)	1912-1993
1912 Edith Porada	1935	1935	1984 w	Austrian-American art historian and archaeologist, a leading authority on ancient cylinder seals	1912-1994
1912 David Feuerwerker	1936		1980	French Jewish rabbi and professor of Jewish history	1912-1980
1912 M. H. Abrams	1936	1940	1983	American literary critic, known for works on romanticism	1912-2015
1912 Milton Singer	1936	1940	1979	Polish -American anthropologist and expert on Indian studies	1912-1994
1912 Robert W. Young	1937		1987	American professor emeritus of linguistics (dictionary on the Navajo language)	1912-2007
1912 Fritz Meier	1937	1937	1982	Swiss Orientalist with a focus on Sufism	1912-1998
1912 Leiva Petersen	1937	1937	1983 w	German classical philologist and publisher	1912-1992
1912 Heinrich Lausberg	1937	1937	1972	German rhetorician, classical philologist and historical linguist specialising in Romance studies	1912-1992
1912 William Bascom	1939	1939	1979	American folklorist, anthropologist, and museum director	1912-1981
1912 Paul K. Benedict	1940	1941	1979	American anthropologist, mental health professional, and linguist who specialized in languages of East and Southeast Asia	1912-1997
1912 George Alexander Kubler	1940	1940	1983	American art historian and among the foremost scholars on the art of Pre-Columbian America and Ibero-American Art	1912-1996
1912 Jean Boisselier	1942		1983	French archaeologist, ethnologist, and art historian	1912-1996
1912 Rosemary Firth	1943 No		1973 w	British social anthropologist in the field of domestic economy	1912-2001
1912 Phyllis Williams Lehmann	1943	1943	1978 w	American classical archaeologist	1912-2004

1912	Maharaia Winiata	1944	1944	1960	New Zealand notable New Zealand tribal leader, Methodist minister, teacher, anthropologist, broadcaster and community leader	1912-1960
1912	Taha Baqir	1945	No	1983	Iraqi archaeologist, author, cuneiformist, linguist, historian, and former curator of the National Museum of Iraq	1912-1984
1912	Gabriel Lasker	1945	1945	1982	British-American biological anthropologist	1912-2002
1912	Sven Arne Runeberg	1945	1947	1979	Finnish anthropologist and linguist, best known for his studies on magic, witchcraft, and sociolinguistics	1912-1979
1912	Tauno Frans Mustanoja	1947	1948	1975	Finnish philologist and scholar of Medieval and Middle English	1912-1996
1912	J. W. B. Barns	1947	1947	1974	British Egyptologist, papyrologist, Anglican priest, and academic	1912-1974
1912	Ghulam Mustafa Khan	1947	1947	1972	Indian researcher, literary critic, linguist, author, scholar of Urdu literature and linguistics, educationist and religious and spiritual leader belonging to Naqshbandi order of Sufism	1912-2005
1912	Wacław Cimochoński	1948	1948	1978	Polish philologist (Indo-European linguistics, especially in Albanology)	1912-1982
1912	Raymond-Jacques Tournay	1948		1981	French Dominican, member of the École Biblique, Biblical scholars and assyriologist	1912-1999
1912	Basil William Robinson	1949		1972	British art scholar and author, specializing in Asian art and history	1912-2005
1912	Schuyler V. R. Cammann	1949	1949	1982	American anthropologist best known for work in Asia	1912-1991
1912	Albert Lord	1949	1949	1983	American professor of Slavic and comparative literature at Harvard University who, after the death of Milman Parry, carried on that scholar's research into epic literature	1912-1991
1912	Moses Finley	1951	1951	1986	American-British academic and classical scholar	1912-1986
1912	Danielle Bonneau	1961	1964	1992 w	French papyrologist	1912-1992
1912	Guillermo Abadía Morales	1963		1983	Colombian linguist, academic, anthropologist, folklore researcher and indigenous language expert	1912-2010
1913	Paul Ricœur	1934	1950	1980	French linguistic philosopher	1913-2005
1913	Vittore Branca	1935	1935	1972	Italian philologist, literary critic and academic	1913-2004

1913	Robert Lumiansky	1935		1983	American scholar of Medieval English and president of the American Council of Learned Societies	1913-1987
1913	Whitney Stoddard	1935	1935	1982	American art historian who specialized in medieval art	1913-2003
1913	José Manuel Blecua Teijeiro	1936	1944	1983	Spanish philologist, professor of Spanish Literature	1913-2003
1913	Alice Mossie Brues	1937	1940	1984 w	American physical anthropologist	1913-2007
1913	René Lacôte	1937		1971	French literary critic, poet and writer	1913-1971
1913	Wolfgang Schmid	1937	1937	1978	German classical philologist	1913-1980
1913	Dorothea Hölscher-Lohmeyer	1937	1937	1991 w	German Germanist and important Goethe researcher	1913-2008
1913	Hans Egon Holthusen	1937	1937	1981	German (Nazi) lyric poet, essayist, and literary scholar	1913-1997
1913	John Adair	1938	1948	1978	American anthropologist (visual anthropology and applied anthropology, culture)	1913-1997
1913	Oswald Szemerényi	1938	1944	1981	Hungarian-British Indo-Europeanist with strong interests in comparative linguistics in general	1913-1996
1913	Hyatt Howe Waggoner	1938	1942	1979	American English professor	1913-1988
1913	Isidore Dyen	1939	1939	1984	Ukrainian-American linguist, Professor Emeritus of Malayo-Polynesian and Comparative Linguistics	1913-2008
1913	Gyula Szepesy	1939	1939	1980	Hungarian linguist	1913-2001
1913	Joe Medicine Crow	1939	No	1982	American Native war chief, author, and historian of the Crow Nation of Native Americans	1913-2016
1913	Cyril Toumanoff	1940	1943	1970	Russian-British Scottish historian and genealogist who mostly specialized in the history and genealogies of medieval Georgia, Armenia, Iran and the Byzantine Empire	1913-1997
1913	Hla Pe	1940	1944	1980	Burmese professor of Burmese language and culture	1913-2007
1913	Lewis Thorpe	1941	No	1977	British philologist and translator	1913-1977
1913	W. Stanford Reid	1941	1941	1978	Canadian professor of history at McGill University and the University of Guelph and a Presbyterian Church in Canada minister	1913-1996
1913	Trygve Heltveit	1942	1942	1981	Norwegian philologist	1913-1985
1913	Charles Wagley	1942	1942	1983	American anthropologist and leading pioneer in the development of Brazilian anthropology	1913-1991

1913	George M. Foster	1942	1942	1979	American anthropologist, best known for contributions on peasant societies (the "principle of limited good" and the "Dyadic Contract") and one of the founders of medical anthropology	1913-2006
1913	Walter Goldschmidt	1942	1942	2002	American anthropologist	1913-2010
1913	David Grene	1942		1982	Irish-American professor of classics	1913-2002
1913	Willem Jacob Verdenius	1942	1942	1978	Dutch Professor of Greek language and literature	1913-1998
1913	Robert Schilling	1945		1982	French historian and Latinist, a specialist in the history of religion in ancient Rome	1913-2004
1913	Robert Fowkes	1946	1947	1978	American linguist (Indo-European Historical Linguistics and philology)	1913-1998
1913	Edward H. Schafer	1947	1947	1984	American historian, sinologist, and writer noted for his expertise on the Tang Dynasty	1913-1991
1913	Arthur F. Wright	1947	1947	1976	American academic, sinologist, editor and professor of history	1913-1976
1913	Leonard Edward Mason	1947	1955	1969	American professor of anthropology at University of Hawaii at Manoa specializing in Pacific Islands of Micronesia	1913-2005
1913	Paul Grice	1948		1979	British philosopher of language (philosophical study of semantics, theory of implicature)	1913-1988
1913	Ali Al-Wardi	1948	1950	1995	Iraqi Social Scientist specialized in the field of Social history	1913-1995
1913	Nicholas Bodman	1949	1950	1979	American linguist (fundamental contributions to the study of historical Chinese phonology and Sino-Tibetan languages)	1913-1997
1913	Arthur Clare Cawley	1949	1952	1979	British literature academic	1913-1993
1913	Richard B. Mather	1949	1949	1984	American Sinologist who was a professor of Chinese	1913-2014
1913	John Collier Jr.	1949	No	1976	American anthropologist and an early leader in the fields of visual anthropology and applied anthropology	1913-1992
1913	Charles Hamilton, Jr.	1950	No	1996	American paleographer, handwriting expert and author of historical works (" philography ")	1913-1996
1913	Derek Kidner	1951		1978	British Old Testament scholar, best known for writing commentaries	1913-2008
1913	Haruhiko Kindaichi	1953	1962	1992	Japanese linguist and a scholar of Japanese linguistics (known as kokugogaku)	1913-2004

1913	Olga Maynard	1957		1984 w	Trinidadian Writer and educator on theater arts, author of articles and monographs on dance and dancers	1913-1994
1914	Martí de Riquer i Morera	1934	1945	1984	Spanish Catalan literary historian and Romance philologist	1914-2013
1914	James Carney	1935	1935	1975	Irish Celtic scholar	1914-1989
1914	Franz Rosenthal	1935	1935	1985	German-American orientalist	1914-2003
1914	María Ugarte	1935	1935	2000 w	Spain-Dominican journalist, writer, academician, historian and palaeographer	1914-2011
1914	Knut Bergsland	1936	1940	1981	Norwegian linguist	1914-1998
1914	Uvo Hölscher	1937	1937	1990	German classical philologist	1914-1996
1914	Rudolf Schnackenburg	1937	1937	1982	German Catholic priest and New Testament scholar	1914-2002
1914	Marvin Opler	1938	1938	1969	American anthropologist and social psychiatrist (study hinted at widespread stresses induced by urban life)	1914-1981
1914	Herbert Hunger	1938	1958	1982	Austrian Byzantinist	1914-2000
1914	Duncan McMillan	1938	1938	1981	British linguist and philologist	1914-1993
1914	Yakov Malkiel	1938	1938	1983	Russian-American Romance etymologist and philologist	1914-1998
1914	Pál Lipták	1938	1938	1980	Hungarian anthropologist, specialized in historical anthropology and Hungarian ethnogenesis	1914-2000
1914	J. C. Hurewitz	1939	1950	1984	American professor emeritus in the political science department	1914-2008
1914	Grete Mostny	1939	1939	1982 w	Austrian-Chilean leading anthropologist	1914-1991
1914	Carl Joachim Hambro	1939	1939	1985	Norwegian novelist, journalist, essayist, translator and Romance philologist	1914-1985
1914	Gérard Garitte	1939		1990	Belgian historian and scientist at the Catholic University of Leuven	1914-1990
1914	Ludvig Holm-Olsen	1940	1940	1981	Norwegian philologist	1914-1990
1914	Polly Hill	1940	1967	1981 w	British social anthropologist of West Africa	1914-2005
1914	Oscar Lewis	1940	1940	1970	American anthropologist	1914-1970
1914	Mary LeCron Foster	1941	1941	1984	American anthropological linguist	1914-2001
1914	Julio Caro Baroja	1942	1942	1985	Spanish anthropologist, historian, linguist and essayist	1914-1995
1914	Abraham M. Halpern	1942	1947	1976	American linguist and anthropologist (Native American Languages)	1914-1985
1914	Edward T. Hall	1942	1942	1977	American anthropologist and cross-cultural researcher	1914-2009
1914	Mohammad Moin	1943	1943	1971	Iranian scholar of Persian literature and Iranian Studies	1914-1971

1914	Parviz Natel-Khanlari	1943	1943	1979	Iranian literary scholar, linguist, author, researcher, politician	1914-1990
1914	Beatrice Blyth Whiting	1943	1943	1980 w	American anthropologist specializing in the comparative study of child development	1914-2003
1914	D. W. Robertson Jr.	1944	1944	1980	American scholar of medieval English literature and especially Geoffrey Chaucer	1914-1992
1914	Jean-Pierre Vernant	1944		1984	French historian and anthropologist, specialist in ancient Greece	1914-2007
1914	Miriam Lichtheim	1944	1944	1974 w	Turkish American-Israeli translator of ancient Egyptian texts	1914-2004
1914	Felicitas D. Goodman	1945	1960	1979 w	American linguist and anthropologist	1914-2005
1914	Muazzez İlmiye Çığ	1945	No	1971 w	Turkish archaeologist and Assyriologist who specializes in the study of Sumerian civilization	1914-2024
1914	Floyd Lounsbury	1946	1949	1979	American linguist, anthropologist and Mayanist scholar and epigrapher, culture and history of the Maya civilization of pre-Columbian Mesoamerica	1914-1998
1914	Silvio Ceccato	1946		1991	Italian philosopher, linguist and academic	1914-1997
1914	Stephen Ullmann	1946	1949	1974	Hungarian linguist	1914-1976
1914	Charles Pellat	1946		1978	French Arabist	1914-1992
1914	Rhoda Metraux	1946	1951	1980 w	American prominent anthropologist in the area of cross-cultural studies	1914-2003
1914	Roman Aftanazy	1946		1987	Polish historian, librarian and author	1914-2004
1914	William Buller Fagg	1947	No	1990	British curator and anthropologist	1914-1992
1914	Emmanuel Laroche	1948	1949	1985	French expert in the languages of ancient Anatolia (Indo-European and Hurrian)	1914-1991
1914	Jean-Michel Guilcher	1948	1948	1979	French ethnologist, and PhD in Dance Studies	1914-2017
1914	Bernard MacGregor Walker Knox	1948	1948	1985	British-American English classicist, author, and critic	1914-2010
1914	Charles Fraser Beckingham	1949		1981	British professor of Islamic Studies	1914-1998
1914	Thomas Berry	1949		1995	American cultural historian and scholar of the world's religions, especially Asian traditions	1914-2009
1914	Matti Kuusi	1950	1950	1977	Finnish folklorist, paremiographer and paremiologist	1914-1998
1914	Jovan Trifunovski	1951	1952	1979	Serbian geographer and anthropologist	1914-1997

1914	Jean Maurice Fiey	1959	1982	1995	French Dominican <i>Father</i> and prominent Church historian and Syriacist	1914-1995
1914	Jean-Pierre Vernant	1962		1984	French historian and anthropologist, specialist in ancient Greece	1914-2007